

SDN-Enabled Continuous-Variable QKD in Coexistence with 8×200 Gb/s 16-QAM Classical Channels

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Abstract— We analyze the coexistence of continuous variable quantum key distribution (CV-QKD) and 8×200 Gb/s 16-QAM classical channels, evaluating parameters such as quantum channel spectral position, classical channel power, guard-band, and the number of exchanged quantum symbols. Additionally, we assess the performance of classical signals in terms of bit error rate (BER) to jointly analyze the impact of coexistence on both classical and quantum channels. These parameters can be exposed to a Software Defined Network (SDN) controller to dynamically optimize the performance of the CV-QKD system. Our results demonstrate that CV-QKD achieves successful key generation with a 100 GHz guard-band with classical channels at -10 dBm and 200 GHz at 0 dBm. The channel position within the spectrum has minimal impact, and lower key rates for short distances do not necessitate asymptotic convergence in quantum symbols. [-20, -10] dBm per channel with 100 GHz guard-band provides error-free classical signals and positive key generation.

Keywords—Continuous variable quantum key distribution (CV-QKD), coexistence, software defined networks (SDN).

I. INTRODUCTION

To fulfil the demands of future 6G networks, the establishment of secure networks is paramount. Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) offers a secure means of generating cryptographic keys based on quantum mechanics, providing security against potential quantum computer threats. However, one challenge in implementing QKD systems is their seamless integration into current networks, without requiring a dedicated QKD network. Thus, QKD needs to operate in coexistence with classical channels, such as in optical fiber links adopting wavelength division multiplexing (WDM). As continuous-variable QKD (CV-QKD) uses optical coherent technology, it is considered a suitable choice for achieving the integration in current telecom infrastructure. Also, Software-Defined Networks (SDN) opens possibilities

for improving the efficiency and dynamic management of coexistence scenarios. By adopting an SDN controller, it is possible to dynamically fine-tune various parameters and configurations, optimizing the performance and resource allocation for both quantum and classical channels/systems [1]. Coexistence scenarios of CV-QKD have been analyzed in prior research considering the fixed International Telecommunication Union (ITU) grid, for example with a 100 GHz spacing. In [2], an experimental demonstration showcased the coexistence of CV-QKD and 7×12.5 Gbit/s on-off keying (OOK). In [3], CV-QKD coexisted with 4×100 Gb/s and 16×10 Gb/s classical telecom signals. Nevertheless, these works primarily focused on lower order modulation formats. In [4] the coexistence of CV-QKD and 89 classical channels separated by 1 nm in C-band transmitted over 7-core fiber is demonstrated.

These studies predominantly concentrated on examining the CV-QKD signals impacted by classical signals. The central focus lies in assessing how the power levels of classical channels influence CV-QKD signals. However, this overlooks the investigation of error-free recovery in classical channels and the power thresholds necessary for error-free transmission of classical signals over specific distances, such as in terms of bit error rate (BER). To achieve a comprehensive analysis, investigation of both classical and CV-QKD signals must be done concurrently. This could help to find the power levels that fulfil the requirements of both classical (in terms of BER) and quantum (in terms of key rate) signals. This can also be critical in dynamically optimizing the coexistence scenario. When a QKD link (optical path between two end points, for example, Alice and Bob) request is received the parameters impacting system's performance can be exposed to an SDN controller to take decisions according to the available resources and the requirements of the system. This optimizes the transmission and maximizes the achievable key rate. It means that SDN controller needs the information of the parameters through which it can base its decision.

This work studies key parameters that can be adjusted by an SDN controller to maximize the efficiency of a quantum system in a WDM scenario considering the ITU grid. Additionally, it considers the successful recovery of classical signals in this context. Specifically, these are: quantum

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Fig. 1 a) Quantum-classical coexistence scenario, and b) CV-QKD coexistence setup

channel spectral-position, classical channel power, guard-band (clearance between classical and quantum channel) and the number of exchanged quantum-symbols. We implement a CV-QKD transmission along with 8×200 Gb/s 16-Quadrature Amplitude Modulation (QAM) classical signals, using VPIphotonics [5] and analyze the effects of these parameters on the performance of the CV-QKD system.

II. SDN-ENABLED CV-QKD IN COEXISTENCE WITH CLASSICAL CHANNELS

The scenario of an SDN-enabled CV-QKD system coexisting with classical channels via WDM is shown in Fig. 1a. The SDN controller supervises the coexistence network and helps optimize the CV-QKD signal from the available information of different parameters. For CV-QKD, a Gaussian-Modulated Coherent State (GMCS) protocol is multiplexed with classical channels in WDM. The CV-QKD system consists of a transmitter, a channel, and a receiver. The key characteristic parameters are transmittance (T) and excess noise (ξ). The transmittance $T=T_{ch} \cdot \eta_{det} \cdot \eta_{coup}$ comprises channel transmittance (T_{ch}) that accounts for attenuation of the signal due to propagation, and detection losses are characterized by the detection efficiency (η_{det}) and coupling efficiency (η_{coup}). The excess noise ξ is the sum of all the possible noise sources such as imperfect modulation, Raman scattering, quantization of analog-to-digital converter, detector's noise, intensity noise, phase noise, crosstalk due to co-propagating channels such as cross phase modulation (XPM) and four wave mixing (FWM) in fiber among others [6]. Assuming a very large number (N) of transmitted quantum-symbols, the secret-key rate can be asymptotically approximated using the Devetak-Winter formula as $K=R \cdot r$, where R is the symbol rate, and r is the secret fraction (bits/symbol) given by $r=\beta I_{AB}-\chi_{EB}$, where I_{AB} is the mutual information between Alice and Bob, β is the reconciliation efficiency of the error correcting code and χ_{EB} is the Holevo bound that represents an upper bound for the available information to the eavesdropper, quantified by the mutual information between Bob's measurements results and Eve's quantum subsystem in a reverse reconciliation protocol. Proving security against collective attacks is sufficient for GMCS CV-QKD due to optimality of Gaussian attacks, and the key rate converges to the asymptotic one for a large N . However, for practical QKD applications, the finite number of exchanged symbols and composability (composition of secure subsystems must be secure) requirements must be considered. This can be addressed by means of a finite-size formalism as presented in [7]. We consider both formalisms in this work.

III. CV-QKD COEXISTENCE SETUP

The setup for the CV-QKD coexistence is shown in Fig. 1b. Alice generates GMCSs (q,p) using a laser source operating at a frequency of 193.4 THz, with a linewidth of 10 kHz. The laser source carrier is modulated by Amplitude

Modulator (AM) and Phase Modulator (PM) and a variable optical attenuator (VOA) at Alice's output to adjust modulation variance (V_{mod}). This work considers $V_{mod} = 6$ shot-noise-units (SNU), based on experiments using LuxQuanta equipment, to balance the trade-off between fiber reach and excess noise at the receiver in presence of transmission impairments from the photonic hardware. Additionally, to investigate the coexistence of quantum and classical signals, eight dual-polarized (DP) classical signals supporting 200 Gb/s with a symbol rate of 32 Gbaud, and a 16-QAM modulation format are created. Before the transmission over a standard single-mode fiber (SSMF), the classical signals are sampled, passed through a root-raised-cosine pulse shaper with a roll-off factor of 0.3, and then multiplexed together with the CV-QKD signal by a 100 GHz-spaced WDM multiplexer (MUX). After fiber propagation either CVQKD or classical signal is analyzed. The CV-QKD signal is filtered out using an optical rectangular bandpass filter (BPF1) with a bandwidth of 50 GHz and stop-band attenuation of 40 dB. Bob performs heterodyne detection using a 90° optical hybrid and two pairs of balanced photodetectors. The local oscillator (LO) laser is derived from transmitter laser using a beam splitter (BS). Note that for link distances longer than the laser coherence length, this setup is equivalent to having two independent lasers. Finally, a parameter estimation process is conducted on the recovered quantum data to determine T , ξ , and r considering $\beta=0.95$. Classical signal is obtained using a bandpass filter (BPF2) with a centre frequency according to the frequency of the channel to be analyzed. After passing through digital signal processing (DSP) which involves chromatic dispersion compensation and phase recovery, BER is calculated.

Fig. 2 r as a function of distance

Fig. 3 Effects of classical channel power on CV-QKD

Fig. 4 Guard-band effects on CV-QKD

IV. RESULTS

The performance evaluation focuses on two key metrics: ξ and r . For ξ we use the noise models proposed in [6]. We assume $\eta_{\text{det}}=\eta_{\text{coup}}=1$, or equivalently $T=T_{\text{ch}}$. First, we analyze the performance of the CV-QKD signal in both the asymptotic regime and adopting finite N . The obtained results are shown in Fig. 2 (green region: keys can be generated and orange region: keys cannot be generated) which represents r as a function of propagation length. It shows that $N>10^{10}$ is sufficient to approximate the asymptotic regime and the CV-QKD system can generate keys up to 25 km. This reach can be increased if V_{mod} is optimized for every target distance which is not the scope of this work. For $N=10^9$ the distance decreases to ~ 19 km, while for $N=10^8$, ~ 8 km can be achieved. This allows the SDN controller optimizing N according to the target distance and r . To analyze the coexistence scenario, and impact of classical channel power, we evenly distribute channels with a 100 GHz spacing between 193 THz and 193.8 THz, while the quantum channel is at 193.4 THz. We investigate three power levels: -30dBm, -10dBm, and 0dBm per classical channel and compare the results to the quantum channel-only scenario, to assess the impact on the quantum channel performance. In the inset of Fig. 3a, we observe spectrum allocation for quantum and classical channels in both standalone and coexistence setups. It also describes that ξ increases as channel power increases which is worse at -10dBm. Results in Fig. 3b demonstrate that considering -30dBm does not impact the CV-QKD and enables a 25 km reach. This is slightly below 25 km when power increases to -10dBm. In Fig. 3c, ξ notably rises for 0dBm, making key generation impossible even within a 1 km distance (Fig. 3d) suggesting that crosstalk have a more significant impact when the CV-QKD signal is close to the WDM channels. The analysis is repeated with a 200 GHz guard-band to see if the performance of CV-QKD system can be improved. When using -10dBm, the performance remains similar to the 100 GHz scenario, as shown in both Fig. 4a and b. However, at 0 dBm there is a notable reduction in ξ (Fig. 4c), obtaining for r to reach a positive value 0.218 bits/symbol over a 10 km link (Fig. 4d). The performance remains the same when guard-band increased to 300 GHz (Fig. 4c and d). This highlights the effectiveness of the guard-band in cases with high classical channel power. This suggests that SDN controller needs to increase the separation between quantum and classical signals when higher power levels are required. Regarding the quantum channel spectral placement, we evenly space channels by 100 GHz between 193 THz and 193.8 THz. We investigate five different positions for the quantum channel:

Fig. 5 Channel placement effects on CV-QKD

193 THz (leftmost), 193.2 THz, 193.4 THz (center channel), 193.6 THz, and 193.8 THz (right-most), each at a power level of -10 dBm per channel. Results as shown in Fig. 5a and b, reveal that the quantum channel position has no impact on CV-QKD performance. In all cases, the achievable distance is slightly below 25 km, indicating that SDN controller can use any available channel as the quantum channel. Table 1 outlines the performance of classical signals while copropagating with CV-QKD signals at 10 km with a spacing of 100 GHz. A forward error correction (FEC) threshold of 1×10^{-2} is considered [7]. BERs of two classical signals at 193.1 THz and 193.7 THz are calculated. The results show that at a very low power of -30 dBm CV-QKD signal has no effect due to the quantum signal (Fig. 2a and b) but classical signals cannot be recovered. However, at 0 dBm CVQKD performs very poorly. This gives the SDN controller a power range from -20 dBm to -10 dBm to achieve good performance of both classical and CV-QKD signals at 10 km. However, it will be interesting to study finer power levels and different link lengths in future.

In short, this work provides guidelines for an SDN-enabled GMCS CV-QKD system coexisting with 8×200 Gb/s, 16-QAM classical channels.

Table 1. Performance of classical signals at 10 km (100 GHz guard-band)

Power/channel (dBm)	Launch Power (dBm)	193.1 THz	193.7 THz	CV-QKD performance
		Error free recovery (classical channels)		
-30	-20.969	No	No	Excellent
-20	-10.969	Yes	Yes	Very Good
-10	-0.969	Yes	Yes	Good
0	9.030	Yes	Yes	Bad

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Svaluto Moreolo, M. Iqbal, L. Nadal and R. Muñoz et al, "Efficient solutions for quantum secure communications in future optical networks," ICTON, 2023.
- [2] T. A. Eriksson et al., "Coexistence of continuous variable quantum key distribution and 7×12.5 Gbit/s classical channels," SUM, 2018.
- [3] T. A. Eriksson et al., "Inter-Core crosstalk impact of classical channels on CV-QKD in Multicore fiber transmission," OFC, 2019.
- [4] X. Wang et al., "Field Trial of $7 \times 89\lambda \times 256$ Gb/s C-Band Classical / CVQKD Co-Existence Transmission over 7-Core Fiber," Asia, ACP/POEM, 2023,
- [5] VPIphotonics. Available online (<https://www.vpiphotonics.com>) (accessed on 05 February 2023).
- [6] F. Laudenbach, et al., "Continuous-variable quantum key distribution with gaussian modulation-the theory of practical implementations," AQT, 2018.
- [7] A. Leverrier, "Composable security proof for continuous-variable quantum key distribution with coherent states," Phys. Rev. Letters, 2015.
- [8] M. Iqbal et al., "Supporting Heterogenous Traffic on Top of Point-to-Multipoint Light-Trees." Sensors, 23, 2023.